

DESIRA: Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas

DISSEMINATION,
COMMUNICATIONS
(DECO) STRATEGY

EXPLOITATION,
AND OUTREACH

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desira

D6.1. Dissemination, Exploitation, Communications and Outreach (DECO) Strategy

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1. Introduction

The Horizon 2020 project DESIRA is adopting an integrated approach to Dissemination, Exploitation, Communications and Outreach activities and tasks which are reflected in this strategy (hereafter called DECO or Communications Strategy). This strategy provides a comprehensive description of the set of communications tools, dissemination channels, engagement actions and outreach activities that help:

- Achieve the overarching project goal;
- Engage effectively and comprehensively with stakeholders;
- Support consortium partners in communications activities;
- Ensure consistency of communications activities within DESIRA;
- Ensure that the project results are fully exploited and widely disseminated, contributing to the project's measurable impact;
- Ensure that all engagement and dissemination activities are interlinked and mutually reinforcing;
- Contribute to creating a recognisable project identity as a reputed stakeholder that can support future action through knowledge and information.

This document goes into the details of the strategy, highlighting:

- The specific aims of DESIRA communications;
- How these aims relate to the main target groups and communications tools identified;
- How the communications tools are targeted at DESIRA stakeholder groups;
- The current strategic approach for each of the DESIRA communication products and their dissemination;
- Overall approach to monitoring, self-assessment and reporting.

The DECO strategy should be understood as a living document. As appropriate, it should evolve over time, especially as a result of new information, opportunities or trends. It will particularly evolve as part of the process of developing greater coordination and synergies between the work of DESIRA, and other H2020 projects, and work of relevant stakeholders on the subject. The long-term aim is to achieve joined-up strategies that support the multiple needs and objectives to support digitisation of rural areas.

This strategy aims at achieving maximum impact, with controlled spending, by selecting channels that are the most effective in reaching out to the various target groups and building upon multipliers, namely consortium partners and relevant stakeholders at EU, national, regional and local level. Multipliers will be invited to share the core messages, practices and ultimately the results of the project using their own communication channels, and tools. The project is built on multipliers as follows:

- Domestically, the multiplier effect is ensured by the involvement of national and regional organisations that have a strong and well-structured presence at local level, and with a widespread and multi-stakeholder membership. The local focus will be reinforced by the international and

cross-country approach, giving a new impetus to the debate and offering new instruments to change the narrative, thanks to exchange of information, models, tools and best practice with partners from other countries;

- At regional level, the multiplier effect will be based on implicating societal actors through regional workshops, starting by looking into current problem and obstacles in order to develop strategic capacity to cope with drivers and barriers.
- At national level, relevant stakeholders for policy analysis will be involved in a “policy process” that will in turn be based on policy audits at regional level and one EU level workshop.
- At European level, the multiplier effect relies first on the involvement of key research and stakeholder organisations that are well networked with EU institutions and networks (e.g. ENRD, EIP, BCO) from within and outside the consortium.

2. DESIRA communications objectives

2.1. Project objectives (POs)

The overarching project objective is to improve the capacity of society and political bodies to respond to the challenges that digitisation generates in rural areas, agriculture and forestry over the next 10 years. In particular, the Consortium will work in an integrated manner to achieve the following project objectives:

- **PO1:** to fill the socio-economic knowledge gaps on digitisation in agriculture, rural areas and forestry;
- **PO2:** to assess the past and current socio-economic impact of digitisation in relation to Sustainable Development Goals;
- **PO3:** to improve the capacity of rural communities to reflect on future risks and opportunities related to digitisation;
- **PO4:** to improve the capacity of rural communities to reap the opportunities offered by digitisation and to improve resilience to related associated risks;
- **PO5:** to promote online interaction and learning – complementary to face-to-face interaction - among a wide range of stakeholders;
- **PO6:** to increase the uptake of societal concerns in ICT-related policy and innovation, and to align digitisation scenarios with societal needs and expectations.

2.2. Communications objectives (COs) and key messages (KMs)

The DECO strategy is key to supporting the project in achieving its objectives. In this respect, the DECO strategy has been designed to achieve the following communication objectives:

- **CO1:** To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation to impact socio-economic development of agricultural, forestry and rural areas and, by extension, their competitiveness in business and market fields;
- **CO2:** To create general social understanding of the power of actively formulating policy options and applicable solutions, as well as enhancing the uptake of policy options that convey societal and environmental concerns;
- **CO3:** Encourage and support innovation, research and knowledge in the field of digitisation of agricultural, forestry and rural areas that also applies the RRI approach (Responsibility in Research and Innovation), which implies openness, inclusiveness, anticipation and responsiveness.

DESIRA's key messages are adapted to each target audience, as explained below, and will be refined over the course of the project. A first set of messages is already proposed:

- **KM1:** Digitisation is an eco-socio-technical transformation;

- **KM2:** The world we live in is a complex system, made out of hybrid systems and entities, linking together people, plants and animals, objects/things, data;
- **KM3:** Different social structures may have different capacities to adapt to the changes generated by ICTs;
- **KM4:** Research and innovation are key drivers of socio-technical transformation;
- **KM5:** Responsibility in research and innovation implies openness, inclusiveness, anticipation and responsiveness;
- **KM6:** Research and innovation in the field of digitisation can bring a key contribution to the achievements of the SDGs.

3. Stakeholder mapping

Good communication is about giving the right information to the right audience at the right time and in the right format. Mapping all the stakeholders and their interest is of capital importance to achieving the DESIRA objectives. Stakeholder mapping links target stakeholders and publics, with the communications and outreach objectives, as well as activities that will facilitate engagement. This detailed mapping allows planning and engagement with stakeholders from the onset of the project, and iteratively co-develop key messages and engage in collaborative data collection, enriching the whole process. This enables the design of targeted communications and dissemination activities that will deliver maximum impact. DESIRA identifies 11 specific target groups for communications activities, illustrated in the following graph (Figure 1).

Figure 1: DESIRA’s main target groups

The following table presents the stakeholder mapping for DESIRA and the communications objectives related to each of them. For each category, key messages, channels and goals are detailed in the table below (Table 2).

Table 1: DESIRA's communications objectives per target audience

Target audience ¹ (WHO)	Communications objectives & Key messages (WHAT)		Outreach channels (WHERE)	DECO actions (HOW)
	Communications objectives	Key messages		
Academia / Research organisations	<p><u>CO3:</u> Encourage and support innovation and research knowledge in the field of digitisation.</p>	<p><u>KM4:</u> Research and innovation are the drivers of socio-technical transformation;</p> <p><u>KM5:</u> Responsibility in research and innovation implies openness, inclusiveness, anticipation and responsiveness;</p> <p><u>KM6:</u> Research and innovation in the field of digitisation can give a key contribution to the achievements of the SDGs.</p>	<p>Rural Digitisation Forum (RDF)</p> <p>Website</p> <p>Social Media</p> <p>Scientific journals</p> <p>Workshops and events</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>VRE</p>	<p>Online interaction via the RDF member group and the Virtual Research Environment (VRE)</p> <p>Policy auditions</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Webinars</p>
Agricultural advisors	<p><u>CO1:</u> To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation;</p> <p><u>CO2:</u> To create general social understanding of the power of actively formulating policy options and applicable solutions, as well as enhancing the uptake of policy options that convey societal and environmental concerns;;</p> <p><u>CO3:</u> Encourage and support innovation and research knowledge in</p>	<p><u>KM1:</u> Digitisation is a socio-technical transformation;</p> <p><u>KM2:</u> The world we live in is made up of hybrid systems, linking together people, objects/things, plants and animals, data;</p> <p><u>KM3:</u> Different social structures may have different capacities to adapt to the changes generated by ICTs;</p> <p><u>KM4:</u> Research and innovation are the drivers of socio-technical transformation;</p> <p><u>KM5:</u> Responsibility in research and innovation implies openness,</p>	<p>RDF</p> <p>Website</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social Media</p> <p>Events</p> <p>VRE</p>	<p>Interaction via the RDF members group and the VRE</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Policy auditions</p> <p>Digital Stories</p> <p>Podcasts</p> <p>Webinars</p>

¹ The target audience listing includes for each listed item individual target audiences as well as related associations (i.e: Farmers and Farmer's Associations).

Target audience ¹ (WHO)	Communications objectives & Key messages (WHAT)		Outreach channels (WHERE)	DECO actions (HOW)
	Communications objectives	Key messages		
	the field of digitisation of agriculture, forestry and rural areas.	inclusiveness, anticipation and responsiveness; <u>KM6:</u> Research and innovation in the field of digitisation can give a key contribution to the achievements of the SDGs.		
EU and National Rural Networks (ENRD, EIP-Agri, BCO)	<p><u>CO1:</u> To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation;</p> <p><u>CO2:</u> To create general social understanding of the power of actively formulating policy options and applicable solutions, as well as enhancing the uptake of policy options that convey societal and environmental concerns;;</p> <p><u>CO3:</u> Encourage and support innovation and research knowledge in the field of digitisation of agriculture, forestry and rural areas.</p>	<p><u>KM1:</u> Digitisation is a socio-technical transformation;</p> <p><u>KM2:</u> The world we live in is made up of hybrid systems, linking together people, objects/things, plants and animals, data;</p> <p><u>KM3:</u> Different social structures may have different capacities to adapt to the changes generated by ICTs;</p> <p><u>KM4:</u> Research and innovation are the drivers of socio-technical transformation;</p> <p><u>KM5:</u> Responsibility in research and innovation implies openness, inclusiveness, anticipation and responsiveness;</p> <p><u>KM6:</u> Research and innovation in the field of digitisation can give a key contribution to the achievements of the SDGs.</p>	RDF Website Newsletter Social Media Events VRE	Interaction via the RDF members group and the VRE Newsletter Policy auditions Digital Stories Podcasts
Rural businesses and services SMEs	<p><u>CO1:</u> To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation;</p>	<p><u>KM1:</u> Digitisation is a socio-technical transformation;</p> <p><u>KM2:</u> The world we live in is made up of hybrid systems, linking together people,</p>	RDF Website Social Media Newsletter	Online interaction via the Virtual Farm Platform (VFP) Short articles

Target audience ¹ (WHO)	Communications objectives & Key messages (WHAT)		Outreach channels (WHERE)	DECO actions (HOW)
	Communications objectives	Key messages		
		objects/things, plants and animals, data; <u>KM3:</u> Different social structures may have different adaptation capacity to the changes generated by ICTs;	Social Media Workshops and events VFP	Press Releases
Public authorities at all levels (including municipalities and local administrations)	<u>CO1:</u> To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation; <u>CO2:</u> To create general social understanding of the power of actively formulating policy options and applicable solutions, as well as enhancing the uptake of policy options that convey societal and environmental concerns.	<u>KM1:</u> Digitisation is a socio-technical transformation; <u>KM2:</u> The world we live in is made up of hybrid systems, linking together people, objects/things, plants and animals, data; <u>KM3:</u> Different social structures may have different adaptation capacity to the changes generated by ICTs; <u>KM4:</u> Research and innovation are the drivers of socio-technical transformation; <u>KM5:</u> Responsibility in research and innovation implies openness, inclusiveness, anticipation and responsiveness; <u>KM6:</u> Research and innovation in the field of digitisation can give a key contribution to the achievements of the SDGs.	RDF Website Workshops and events Living Labs VRE/VFP Social Media Newsletter	Policy Auditions Online interaction via the VRE/VFP and the RDF members group Campaigning actions
Citizen groups Local communities Local associations	<u>CO1:</u> To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation;	<u>KM1:</u> Digitisation is a socio-technical transformation; <u>KM2:</u> The world we live in is made up of hybrid systems, linking together people,	RDF Website Social Media Newsletter	Policy Auditions Online interaction via the RDF members

Target audience ¹ (WHO)	Communications objectives & Key messages (WHAT)		Outreach channels (WHERE)	DECO actions (HOW)
	Communications objectives	Key messages		
	<p><u>CO2:</u> To create general social understanding of the power of actively formulating policy options and applicable solutions, as well as enhancing the uptake of policy options that convey societal and environmental concerns.</p>	<p>objects/things, plants and animals, data; <u>KM3:</u> Different social structures may have different adaptation capacity to the changes generated by ICTs;</p>	<p>Workshops and Events Media VFP</p>	<p>group and VFP Photo contest Videos Podcasts Digital Stories Newsletter</p>
<p>Digital technology operators</p>	<p><u>CO1:</u> To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation; <u>CO3:</u> Encourage and support innovation and research knowledge in the field of digitisation of agriculture, forestry and rural areas.</p>	<p><u>KM3:</u> Different social structures may have different adaptation capacity to the changes generated by ICTs; <u>KM4:</u> Research and innovation are the drivers of socio-technical transformation; <u>KM5:</u> Responsibility in research and innovation implies openness, inclusiveness, anticipation and responsiveness; <u>KM6:</u> Research and innovation in the field of digitisation can give a key contribution to the achievements of the SDGs.</p>	<p>RDF Website Social Media Newsletter Workshops and Events Media</p>	<p>Online interaction via the RDF members group and VRE Short articles Press releases</p>
<p>Farmers, foresters and agri-food sector</p>	<p><u>CO1:</u> To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation; <u>CO2:</u> To create general social understanding of the power of actively</p>	<p><u>KM1:</u> Digitisation is a socio-technical transformation; <u>KM2:</u> The world we live in is made up of hybrid systems, linking together people, objects/things, plants and animals, data; <u>KM3:</u> Different social structures may have</p>	<p>RDF Website Social Media Newsletter Workshops and Events VFP</p>	<p>Policy Auditions Online interaction via the RDF members group and VFP Videos</p>

Target audience ¹ (WHO)	Communications objectives & Key messages (WHAT)		Outreach channels (WHERE)	DECO actions (HOW)
	Communications objectives	Key messages		
	formulating policy options and applicable solutions, as well as enhancing the uptake of policy options that convey societal and environmental concerns.	different adaptation capacity to the changes generated by ICTs;		Podcasts Digital Stories Newsletter Photo contest
Investors and other businesses	<u>CO1:</u> To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation; <u>CO3:</u> Encourage and support innovation and research knowledge in the field of digitisation of agriculture, forestry and rural areas.	<u>KM1:</u> Digitisation is a socio-technical transformation; <u>KM2:</u> The world we live in is made up of hybrid systems, linking together people, objects/things, plants and animals, data;	RDF Website Workshops and events Living Labs Social Media Newsletter	Online interaction via the RDF members group Short articles Press releases Videos Podcasts Digital Stories
University Students	<u>CO1:</u> To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation; <u>CO2:</u> To create general social understanding of the power of actively formulating policy options and applicable solutions, as well as enhancing the uptake of policy options that convey societal and environmental concerns	<u>KM1:</u> Digitisation is a socio-technical transformation; <u>KM2:</u> The world we live in is made up of hybrid systems, linking together people, objects/things, plants and animals, data; <u>KM3:</u> Different social structures may have different adaptation capacity to the changes generated by ICTs; <u>KM4:</u> Research and innovation are the drivers of socio-technical transformation; <u>KM5:</u> Responsibility in research and innovation implies openness,	RDF Website Social Media Workshops and Events VRE/VFP Newsletter	Online interaction via the RDF members group, VRE and VFP Videos Podcasts Digital Stories Newsletter Photo contest

Target audience ¹ (WHO)	Communications objectives & Key messages (WHAT)		Outreach channels (WHERE)	DECO actions (HOW)
	Communications objectives	Key messages		
		inclusiveness, anticipation and responsiveness; <u>KM6:</u> Research and innovation in the field of digitisation can give a key contribution to the achievements of the SDGs.		
Media	<p><u>CO1:</u> To build a robust and long-lasting collective awareness on the role and opportunities of digitisation;</p> <p><u>CO2:</u> To create general social understanding of the power of actively formulating policy options and applicable solutions, as well as enhancing the uptake of policy options that convey societal and environmental concerns.</p>	<p><u>KM1:</u> Digitisation is a socio-technical transformation;</p> <p><u>KM2:</u> The world we live in is made up of hybrid systems, linking together people, objects/things, plants and animals, data;</p> <p><u>KM3:</u> Different social structures may have different adaptation capacity to the changes generated by ICTs;</p>	Workshops and Events Social Media Media Newsletter	Press Kit Media relations

4. DESIRA outreach channels

The outreach channels are selected to convey the key messages and outcomes of the project to the largest possible number of stakeholders and target group members. The strategy will work through both information pull and information push and will include various tools designed to reach different kinds of target groups through the following dissemination channels:

- Website
- Virtual Research Environment (VRE)
- Rural Digitisation Forum (RDF)
- Social Media
- Scientific Journals
- Media
- Newsletter
- Workshops & Events

4.1. Website

The DESIRA Website will host all official information on the project. It is conceived as a hub containing and redirecting to every communications tool, channel and activity. The portal will be created and maintained at the URL www.desira2020.eu and regularly updated by the coordinator with the contribution of the communications team in order to present relevant and timely information about the project, including news, public documents, publications and presentations, etc.

Website sections serve to promote the content of the project such as introduction, project structure, partners, deliverables, events, and news that will be fed from different sources, such as partners' contributions and subjects linked to current societal issues related to digitisation. The website will link to the RDF, the VRE and to all social media channels opened for the project. A sign-up box for subscribing to the Rural Digitisation Forum will be accessible through the homepage.

4.2. Virtual Research Environment & Virtual Farm Platform

DESIRA will develop a working environment tailored to the needs of the project: A Virtual Research Environment (VRE) will connect participants and allow substantial interactions within the network. It will serve to share data, outputs and tools, and contribute to dissemination and communications. The VRE complements face-to-face interactions by promoting online exchange and learning among the wide range of stakeholders that form the RDF members group, and it provides easy and open access to research findings, supporting tools for knowledge exchange (in line with RRI principle "increase access to scientific

results”). The VRE will facilitate the development of the Living Labs and the RDF as virtual communities, providing the necessary tools to overcome language barriers by using both human and automated translation services. Communications flows and learning processes within the VRE will be planned, monitored, assessed and reported.

DESIRA will further develop the Virtual Farm Platform (VFP), a proof of concept developed in the H2020 PLAID project. The VFP is a virtual environment, developed through virtual reality technology, that users can navigate in order to access information, educational resources, and inspiration for digital opportunities applicable to their own needs and contexts. These resources will be adapted according to the findings from the first three WPs, in order to ensure the VFP has a powerful impact for rural stakeholders and to enable new forms of engagement and learning about digital opportunities for agriculture, forestry and rural development. This will be done through on-line, 360-degree interaction with videos and other outputs.

4.3. EU Rural Digitisation Forum

The EU Rural Digitisation Forum (RDF) is a central element of the DESIRA project. In practice, the RDF is both a virtual and physical forum that comes alive through the implementation of a series of meetings, webinars, working groups, and exchanges through online platforms among its members. As such, the Rural Digitisation Forum is considered a key dissemination channel as well as one of the key elements for stakeholder engagement. As a dissemination channel, the RDF will be composed of members that register through an open call for membership. Registration will happen on a voluntary basis, through an online form that will allow all those interested in joining the forum to register their profile (personal and contact details, affiliation, field of work, fields of interest) and their desired involvement (participation in activities or information exchange only). The project will comply with the GDPR regulation.

As a result of the registrations of members, the RDF members' group list will be compiled. This distribution list will be used for:

- Sending invitations to participate in the RDF meetings, webinars and other relevant events;
- Disseminating the main DESIRA communications outputs such reports, briefs, videos, research papers, RDF report highlights, etc.

The RDF will kick-start with a call for interest that will be shared among partners, key stakeholders and networks. The open call will be launched through key communications channels (social media, website) and will try and engage relevant networks and stakeholders working to achieve a wide outreach (e.g. EIP, ENRD, BCO, etc.). The aim is to achieve **at least 250 members**.

In addition to the RDF mailing list, dedicated RDF communities on Facebook will be permanently established through the creation of private groups (membership on request) as a base for the exchange of content and ideas, and will provide the opportunity to get feedback from like-minded individuals. Each platform is intended to reach diverse audiences and profiles. The purpose of these groups is to provide a space for a two-way communication where interested stakeholders in the field of digitisation can provide information about events, news, publications etc. Experience tells us that these groups are likely to attract the interest of a wider community around the EU, representing a very suitable channel for the dissemination of DESIRA's main communications products and information. The aim is to achieve at least 450 members.

4.4. Social Media

The extensive use of social media is aimed at increasing the awareness of potential users and encouraging them to download the project's outputs. Each channel is intended to reach a specific audience, and the messages will be adapted accordingly.

Social media is intended to act as an accelerator of the discussion, exchange and adoption of “socio-cyber-physical” systems in agriculture, forestry and rural areas; different social media channels will trigger snowball/networking effect and enable the project to reach beyond its ‘usual suspects’ audience. The various Social Media profiles are selected to reaching out to a wide and relevant audience. The content shared on each platform will include different types of outputs and will redirect and feed traffic to the main website.

- **Twitter** @DESIRA_H2020 - this channel is used for short news flashes, using a clear and crisp style, not too descriptive or institutional. It will also play an important role during events, where live tweeting will be enabled. Live tweeting will participate in creating a knowledge community linking participants, panel and experts, as well as audiences following the event remotely.
- **Facebook** 'DESIRA H2020'- this channel will be adopted for public outreach and showcasing outputs. Events and Photo album functionalities will be exploited. Facebook will also host a permanent group (membership on request) of the Rural Digitisation Forum that will enable the RDF community to share experiences, events, studies, news and relevant information with peers.
- **Instagram** @DESIRA_H2020 - this channel is used to share visual outputs (i.e. on the ground snapshots shared by project partners) and also for ad-hoc actions such as the photo contest.
- **LinkedIn** - this channel will be used to promote cooperation and support matchmaking between stakeholders and a wide audience of professional stakeholders. Selected articles, news pieces, digital stories and other communications content will also be shared on this platform. LinkedIn will also host a permanent group (membership on request) of the Rural Digitisation Forum that will enable the RDF community to share experiences, events, studies, news and relevant information with peers.
- **YouTube** - the dedicated YouTube channel will be used to publish and collect all the project's multimedia products. Videos will be embedded via YouTube on the website, and easily shared on social media through short links.
- **ResearchGate / Academia Edu** - these channels will be used to disseminate scientific papers and any research output produced by the project, as they are largely used by researchers.

Supporting visual material will be used in different social media channels in order to highlight messages. In general, appealing visuals will help catch the attention of the followers/audience, and invite them to read more and learn more about the proposed topic. For instance, video teasers shared on social media will invite the target audience to watch the full videos. The illustrative elements, such as banners for social media profiles, will help create a brand consistency and a visual identity for the project.

4.5. Scientific Journals

The industrial and academic partners will individually and collaboratively publish and present scientific advances in technical papers as well as in peer-reviewed journals. This dissemination activity addresses thus the RRI principle “increase access to scientific results” and it will be targeted mainly at the scientific community.

Publications in specialised magazines and papers sent to related events will attract the attention of researchers and practitioners. Joint publications will be encouraged, and an ad-hoc working group within the consortium, composed of WP leaders, will be set up to coordinate participation at scientific conferences. The table below (Table 2) outlines some of the key scientific journals and the publications that will be targeted. These scientific journals have been selected for their reputation and importance in the field of digitisation of agriculture, forestry and rural areas.

Table 2. Targeted scientific journals

Target Journal/Magazines	Number of expected publications and expected date delivery	
	20 peer-reviewed publications	
European review of Agricultural Economics, Agriculture and Human Values, Sociologia Ruralis, Journal of Rural Studies, Sustainability, Land Use Policy, Agriculture and Food Economics, European Journal of Forest Research, Agribusiness, Eurochoices, Research Policy, IEEE Access, IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials	#1 at month 15 (D1.1) #2 at month 24 (D1.3) #3 at month 24 (D2.1) #4 at month 36 (D3.1) #5 at month 36 (D2.2) #6-12month 36 (WD2.2 and WD3.2)	#13 at month 36 (D4.1) #14 at month 42 (D2.3) #15-17 at month 42 (D3.3) #18 at month 48 (D3.4) #19-21 at month 48 (D5.4)

4.6. Media

The purpose of using general and specialised media content is to reach both the general public and a more specific audience with key information in the field of digitisation of agriculture, forestry and rural areas.

We will use partners’ existing media contact lists to develop and implement press and public relation activities. The subscription to [Anewstip](#) provides an extensive media contact database and allows monitoring of news articles. The consortium will approach certain media to explore the possibility of publishing articles and interviews. Engaging with the press (from EU to local level) will also be key to preparing DESIRA events, in Brussels as well as in other countries, regions and municipalities. Dedicated press kits will be delivered to all journalists participating in DESIRA events. DESIRA, through AEIDL and Cultivate, will also launch media and public relations campaigns, draft press releases and connect with newsrooms.

4.7. Newsletter

The newsletter aims to communicate project content, serving as a 'reminder call' of the project to all subscribers. Every four months, it provides project news and includes links to the DESIRA social media accounts, where subscribers are invited to join for quicker daily updates.

All newsletters will be stored in a dedicated section on the website. The design will follow the DESIRA visual identity, and will help reinforce the brand recognition of the project.

The information will originate from the central team, as well as from the research teams of the consortium, including each partner's liaison officer in charge of communications. An effort will be made to put as much emphasis as possible on practitioners, through on-the-ground reports, user-provided feedback from DESIRA events and actions.

A structure will be defined and fed accordingly, but there will be a certain flexibility in order to publish timely newsletters according to the different developments of the project.

Table 3: Main structure of the newsletter

Section	Content
Leading article	Expert-led article about a specific topic of interest around digitisation and DESIRA outcomes. These leading articles will help to communicate the key message of DESIRA.
News	Highlight of one piece of news, including main ideas, future perspectives, link to DESIRA, picture + link to news section on the website.
Stakeholder perspectives	Short stakeholder articles on specific and relevant topics related to DESIRA. They aim to provide snappy and brief information about key hot topics related to the digitisation of agriculture, forestry and rural areas. These articles will link to specific outputs from DESIRA (e.g. policy briefs, game changers, etc.).
Partners' highlight	A partners' profile will be featured + link to partners section of the website.
Upcoming events	A calendar of upcoming public actions and events, including relevant links when necessary.

4.8. Workshops and Events

4.8.1. DESIRA workshops and events

The DESIRA project will organise a wide diversity of events, including 15 national conferences and 60 regional workshops and one final international conference. These events are a central part of the project and by extension a key channel for dissemination and opportunity to engage with stakeholders. Events will be conceived through a participatory approach and will integrate interactive elements such as instant surveys and real time visualisation tools; they will be tailored around maximising the 'Living Lab logic' concept (design thinking, co-creation sections, visual reporting techniques). The communications team will

be closely involved in the organisation of the events, designing the specific communications activities for each. These associated activities include those pre-event, during the event and post event.

4.8.2. Third party events

DESIRA plans to have project presentations at scientific conferences targeting relevant domains for the project. The impact of presentations at this kind of event is very high because of the attendance of scientists, industrial experts and representatives of international and national public authorities.

Workshops, meetings and other large events (summer and winter schools for academic students, scientific exhibitions, trade fairs, showcases, ICT OPEN DAYS) represent relevant and important opportunities for DESIRA dissemination. All this complies with the RRI principle to “increase access to scientific results”.

The goal of these events will be to disseminate both the techniques developed during the project and the preliminary results of the project to DESIRA's targeted beneficiaries. The DESIRA target conferences and events are summarised in the table below (Table 4), which will be continuously updated during the regular communications meetings, with newly identified events.

Table 4: Identified third party events

Name of event	Target audience	Location, number of events, date
European Society of Rural Sociology	Scientists, stakeholders, public authorities	2019-2021-2023
EAAE European Association of Agricultural economics		2020-2022-2024
IFSA International Farming Systems Association		2020-2022-2024
IRSA International Rural Sociology Association		2022-2024
ESOF Euro Science Open Forum		
National scientific conferences		
IEEE IoT Vertical and Topical Summit for Agriculture		
ESOF Euro Science Open Forum		2022
National scientific conferences	2019-2024	

In addition, DESIRA will aim to participate in other third-party events related to the digitisation of agriculture, forestry and rural areas, such as those organised by European and national networks such as EIP or ENRD, in which active participation will be encouraged in order to present the outcomes of the projects (e.g. key messages).

5. DESIRA Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation products

5.1. Overview of DESIRA Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation products

DESIRA will develop targeted products that will be communicated through the relevant outreach channels described above. These products are designed in a way to maximise its usefulness for the targeted audience.

According to the European Intellectual Property Rights Helpdesk in the document “*Making the most of your H2020 project*”², we can define the key terms relating to engagement actions as follows:

Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
“Communication on projects is (...) aimed at promoting the action and its results . It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”	“Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”	“Exploitation refers to the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”

Taking this into consideration, the following tables (Tables 6, 7 and 8) summarise the main communications, dissemination and exploitation products developed by DESIRA, their target audience, main outreach channels and KPIs.

Table 5. Overview of communications products [Dissemination (R&I)]

Key product	Description/Purpose	Target Audience	Outreach Channel
(1) Conceptual and Analytical Framework (CAF) report - <i>Month 46</i>	A report identifying the most relevant concepts and relations, key hypotheses, key analytical questions	Research and academia (including students) Agricultural advisors	Website VRE RDF Social Media Workshops & Events

² European IPR Helpdesk. (2018). Making the most of your H2020 project. [online] Available at: https://www.iprhelphdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E_0.pdf [Accessed 31 Jul. 2019].

Key product	Description/Purpose	Target Audience	Outreach Channel
			Newsletter
(300) Digital Game Changers	300 digital projects initiatives and technologies applied in the rural, agriculture or forestry context.	Local practitioners and SMEs Farmers Policy makers European and national networks (ENRD, EIP, BCO, NRNs, etc.) Agricultural advisors	Website Media RDF Social Media Workshops & Events Newsletter
(1) Synthesis report on the Taxonomy and Inventory of Digital Game Changers (DGC) – <i>month 16</i>	A report illustrating the most relevant categories for ICTs (potentially) applied to agriculture, forestry and rural areas.	Research and academia (including students) Agricultural advisors Local practitioners and SMEs Farmers	Website VRE RDF Scientific journals Social Media Workshops & Events
(1) Pan-European report on rural digitisation (PEA) – <i>Month 20</i>	The report will provide an overview on state of rural digitisation and its socio-economic impact based on the analysis of the digitisation index and of its correlation with performance of rural areas in Europe.	Policy makers; European and national stakeholder working in this field Research and academia	Website VRE RDF Social Media Workshops & Events Scientific Journals
(20) Needs, Expectations and Impact (NEI) report and (1) synthesis report – <i>month 20 & 26</i>	A synthesis of the 20 NEI regional reports with a comparative analysis of socio-economic impacts of digitisation, in the light of the Conceptual and Analytical Framework.	Policy makers European and national stakeholder working in this field Research and academia	Website VRE RDF Social Media Workshops & Events
(20) LL Scenario reports and (1) Comparative Scenario Report – <i>month 30 and EU level scenario report</i>	The report will contain a synthesis of the scenario development of the 20 Living Labs.	Policy makers Research and academia European and national stakeholder working in this field	Website RDF Scientific Journals Social Media Workshops & Events
(20) Policy briefs – <i>month 30</i>	Short documents (in EIP format) illustrating the characteristics of the most relevant issues emerging in the scenario development exercise in the Living Labs.	Policy makers European and national stakeholder working in this field	Website RDF Social Media Workshops & Events
(80) Digital stories	80 digital stories (four for each Living Lab) will be released on the web will describe the four scenarios of each Living Labs.	Research and academia (including students) EU and National Rural Networks Rural businesses and services SMEs	Website RDF Social Media Media Workshops & Events

Key product	Description/Purpose	Target Audience	Outreach Channel
		Public authorities Citizen groups and local communities Digital technology operators Farmers, foresters and agri-food sector Media	Newsletter
(1) Showcase technology report – <i>month 48</i>	Report on technology development based on the findings of the Living Labs and of the related Use Cases.	Research and academia Digital technology operators Rural business and services	Website VRE/VFP RDF Scientific journals Social media Workshops & Events Newsletter
(20) National policy reports – <i>month 31</i>	Review of the existing policy mix at local, regional and national level associated to the digitisation in rural areas, and outcomes of the policy auditions.	Policy makers Living Labs	Website VRE RDF Scientific journals Social media Media Workshops & Events Newsletter
(21) Scientific articles	Publications in specialised magazines, papers sent to related events and joint publications to disseminate high-level project information and to attract the interest of representatives of the various target groups.	Research and academia (including students) European and national stakeholder working in this field	Website VRE Social Media Media Scientific journals Workshops & Events Newsletter

Table 6: Overview of communications products [Communication]

Key product	Description/Purpose	Target Audience	Outreach Channel
(10) Short articles – <i>month 46</i>	Texts of about 1000-1500 words about the main project messages, the Living Lab focal questions, the digital stories and the Use Cases.	Research and academia (including students) EU and National Rural Networks Rural businesses and services SMEs Public authorities Citizen groups and local communities Digital technology operators Farmers, foresters and agri-food sector	Website RDF Social Media Media Workshops & Events

Key product	Description/Purpose	Target Audience	Outreach Channel
(5) Video interviews	Video interviews on Taxonomy and inventory of digital game changers with high-level experts.	Media Research and academia (including students) EU and National Rural Networks Rural businesses and services SMEs Public authorities Citizen groups and local communities Digital technology operators Farmers, foresters and agri-food sector Media	Website VRE RDF Social Media Workshops & Events Newsletter Media
(5) Webinar	Short online seminars on DESIRA outputs.	Research and academia (including students) EU and National Rural Networks Rural businesses and services SMEs Public authorities Citizen groups and local communities Digital technology operators Farmers, foresters and agri-food sector	Website RDF Social Media Media Workshops & Events Newsletter
Podcasts	Voice recordings giving voice to the participants at the Living Labs and the Rural Digitisation Forum and familiarising a broad public with the variety of regional contexts.	Research and academia (including students) EU and National Rural Networks Rural businesses and services SMEs Public authorities Citizen groups and local communities Digital technology operators Farmers, foresters and agri-food sector	Website RDF Social Media Media Workshops & Events Newsletter
Newsletter	Provide information on recent activities of DESIRA, originating from the central team as well as from researchers of the consortium.	Research and academia (including students) EU and National Rural Networks Rural businesses and services SMEs Public authorities Citizen groups and local communities Digital technology operators Farmers, foresters and agri-food sector Media	Website RDF Social Media Workshops & Events
Video / photo elements	Leverage co-creation within the network and, using social media, amplify	Research and academia (including students) EU and National Rural Networks	Website Social Media Workshops & Events

Key product	Description/Purpose	Target Audience	Outreach Channel
	visibility of the message, stakeholders as well as the network itself.	Rural businesses and services SMEs Public authorities Citizen groups and local communities Digital technology operators Farmers, foresters and agri-food sector Media	Newsletter
Press releases	Documents addressed to media compiling key data about DESIRA project in relation to events where the project will be presented.	Research and academia (including students) EU and National Rural Networks Rural businesses and services SMEs Public authorities Citizen groups and local communities Digital technology operators Farmers, foresters and agri-food sector Media	Website Social Media Media Workshops & Events Newsletter

Table 7: Overview of communications products [Exploitation]

Key product	Description/Purpose	Target Audience	Outreach Channel
(1) Ethical code – month 46	The report will include a review of ethical codes and their use. In the final DESIRA conference, the consortium member, SL members, as well as RDF will refine, finalise and sign the Ethical Code on Digitisation.	Research and academia Digital technology operators Policy makers	Website VRE RDF Social media Newsletter
Training Kit	The Training Kit will develop capacity and enable ongoing impact assessment and scenario development in rural areas and accelerate knowledge creation beyond those in direct contact with the project.	Students Rural business and services Local communities Stakeholder organisations Digital technology operators	Website VRE Social Media Workshops & Events

Key product	Description/Purpose	Target Audience	Outreach Channel
(50) DGC Practice Abstracts (PA) – <i>month 16</i>	Short documents (in EIP format) illustrating the characteristics of the most relevant DGCs.	Local practitioners and SMEs Farmers Policy makers European and national networks (ENRD, EIP, BCO, NRNs, etc.) Agricultural advisors Investors	Website VRE RDF Social Media Workshops & Events
(1) Socio-Economic Sustainability Indicators (SESI) report and tool– <i>month 36</i>	A report illustrating a set of indicators on which socio-economic assessment of digitisation will be carried out and the methodology for their measurement.	Policy makers European and national stakeholders working in this field Research and academia Investors	Website VRE RDF Social Media Workshops & Events
(5) Use Case and Showcase technology + (1) Practice Abstract (PA) – <i>month 48</i>	Description of the socio-cyber-physical systems addressing the problems identified by five selected Living Labs. Six short documents (in EIP format) with a synthesis of Use Cases and showcase technology.	Citizen groups and local communities Digital technology operators Farmers, foresters and agri-food sector Rural business and services Investors	Website VRE/VFP RDF Social media Workshops & Events Newsletter
(1) Report on Policy analysis and roadmap – <i>month 46</i>	The Policy Analysis and Roadmap will provide policy makers and rural change makers with a sound understanding of the policy implications of digitisation in rural areas and the issues needing policies and actions.	Policy makers Digital technology operators Rural business and services	Website VRE RDF Social Media Workshops & Events Newsletter

6. Stakeholder Engagement Actions

Participation and the engagement of stakeholders is a core principle of the DESIRA project. This principle is embedded in all the activities implemented throughout the project to achieve reliable and accountable outputs relevant for European society. This also ensures that the results of the project cover and address the needs and expectation of the rural community. Several actions are carefully designed to ensure the engagement of rural stakeholders throughout the project mainly through:

- Virtual Research Environment (VRE)
- EU Rural Digitisation Forum (RDF)
- Living Labs
- DESIRA Events (workshops and conferences)
- Training

The above actions also ensure the engagement with other relevant project projects working in this field of digitisation of agriculture, forestry and rural areas, including the projects funded by H2020, such the ones supported under the RUR01 call.

6.1. Virtual Research Environment

A Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is a web-based working environment tailored to serve the needs of a community of practice, providing the whole array of tools needed to accomplish the community's goal(s). DESIRA will use a VRE to share data, outputs and tools, to connect researchers and stakeholders, and to contribute to dissemination and communications. The VRE will also serve the needs of the Living Labs. The VRE is a infrastructure for communications purposes that is ready to be deployed from the start of the project. It will be equipped and provide access to the following facilities via a dedicated portal:

- Private cloud storage area, equipped with an easy-to-use workspace application designed for use by a wide set of different actors, and the capability to store either private or shared data;
- Social networking applications, where each project member will have the possibility to share posts (text, images, and files annotated with hashtags) with VRE members and to collect them in a dedicated news feed (as in Twitter and Facebook). These applications are conceptually close to the common ones promoted by social networks – e.g. posting news, commenting on posted news – yet adapted to promote large-scale collaboration and cooperation on comprehensive scientific products, data sets, theories and tools;
- Private messaging applications integrated with the cloud storage; and
- Activity tracker and collaborative wiki.

The VRE is mainly targeted at project members to coordinate and facilitate their participation in the project.

6.2. EU Rural Digitisation Forum

The EU Rural Digitisation Forum (RDF) is a central element of the DESIRA project. It represents an open space for discussion and exchange with key experts and the wider community interested in the digitisation of agriculture, forestry and rural areas. Through this forum, rural stakeholders will support the project in its research activities (e.g. identifying the game changers, building the conceptual framework, providing expertise and contacts in the field and developing the socio-economic impact assessment reports) as well in its communications and dissemination activities.

In practice, the RDF is both a virtual and physical forum that comes alive through the implementation of a series of meetings, webinars, working groups, and exchanges through online platforms among its members. The DESIRA project will build on the topics and information shared on the group, while also feeding content to the forum by relaying outputs and results achieved during the project cycle.

It will be organised in four interacting working groups (WG) on:

1. WG1: Digitisation of 'agriculture'
2. WG2: Digitisation of 'forestry'
3. WG3: Digitisation of 'rural areas/life'
4. WG4: Digitisation 'policies'

The WGs of the RDF will co-develop ideas, scenarios, and socio-technical solutions related to digitisation in specific study contexts. In particular, three of the working groups of the RDF (rural areas/life, agriculture and forestry) will support the Consortium in the Comparative Scenario Assessment (CSA). The policy working group will deal with policy analysis.

In practice, the RDF is built on a composite of physical and virtual platforms to ensure participation and the engagement of the DESIRA community. The virtual platform will be developed in the VRE composed with experts from within DESIRA (and key external experts). In addition, a private Facebook group (membership on request) will be permanently established as a base for the exchange of content and ideas, and provide the opportunity to get feedback from like-minded individuals from outside the DESIRA consortium.

The physical platform is represented by the three meetings of the RDF, which will be implemented by specific WP leaders (ILVO; UNIPI; HUTTON and UCO) and supported by AEIDL. Each of the meetings will be articulated between plenary sessions and working groups, and will be facilitated so as to maximize the interaction. A total of up to 35 participants will engage in each of the meetings. The composition of the participants will represent a balance of stakeholders.

Table 10 compiles key information for a better understanding of the three RDF meetings:

Table 8: Rural Digitisation Forum (RDF)

RDF meetings	Period	Target audience	Outcomes
RDF Meeting 1	Month 14-15	Researchers Policy makers Stakeholder organisations and networks SMEs	Contribution to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conceptual and Analytical Framework (CAF) version I • Draft Taxonomy and Inventory of Digital Game Changers (TGC) • First list of Socio-Economic Sustainability Indicators (SESI) • Draft Pan-European digitisation assessment report (PEA)
RDF Meeting 2	Month 25-26	Researchers Policy makers Stakeholder organisations and networks	Contribution to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparative Scenario assessment (CSA) report • Needs, Expectations and Impacts report • SESI synthesis reports
RDF Meeting 3	Month 41-42	Policy makers Stakeholder organisations and networks Researchers	Contribution to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Analysis and Policy Roadmap reports

The conclusions of the discussions in the RDF will be fed into different outputs of DESIRA. An RDF report (with minutes) will be produced after each meeting including the contribution of each of the partners organising the meetings. The use of the most innovative reporting techniques will be encouraged, including infographics and visual notetaking that helps capture all the inputs to the discussions. If relevant, a summary version (2-4 pages highlights report) of the RDF report will be produced, providing the key messages and outcomes of the meeting in a more user-friendly and attractive manner. This will serve to disseminate its results to a wide range of stakeholders, particularly the RDF members. In addition, other specific communications products can be developed to communicate further the key messages and outcomes of the RDF meetings, such as news items and short articles.

6.3. Living Labs

Living Labs (LLs) are defined as user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings. Living Labs will be implanted in 20 European regions and will be networks of rural businesses and services,

public authorities, citizen groups, digital technology operators, farmers, media operators and researchers who co-develop ideas, scenarios, and socio-technical solutions related to digitisation in specific study contexts such as rural areas, supply chains, and sectors of activity. They will include both already active 'informal'/bottom up networks and already 'formalised' networks (such as Digital Innovation Hubs, Technology Cluster or EIP Operational Groups) will play a key role in providing information and opinions, validating methodologies, developing scenarios, co-designing Use Cases and Showcase technologies.

Living Labs will be composed of around 20 members each, selected via a stakeholder analysis carried out on the basis of 5-10 interviews. Members of the Living Labs will be invited to create a virtual community within the DESIRA Environment, which will allow online interaction among members of the lab. Each community will nominate a moderator.

Work package leaders will develop guidelines and templates for data collection and workshop facilitation, including training sessions to support local teams when needed. These measures will ensure maximum participation and engagements of all relevant stakeholders.

The Living Labs are also related to the work of the RDF and its stakeholders are key components of the RDF and vice versa (see figure 2). Both will feed into each other in terms of knowledge and information. For instance, the results and outputs of the Living Labs, such as podcasts, short articles and digital stories, will be widely disseminated to the members of the RDF. Likewise, the outputs of RDF will be disseminated to the Living Labs and its stakeholders.

Figure 2: Interaction between LLs and the RDF

Living Labs will discuss the past and present problems related to digitisation in the domain defined by the focal question, will develop four future scenario narratives to discuss what would happen (for example, who would be winners, who the losers, who the opponents) in the selected domain defined by the focal question of the Living Lab, and to identify the most promising ICT-based solution. Scenario workshops will be held by Living Labs in 20 European regions (month 18-24). Workshops comprise 10-15 participants, split into 2-3 groups. A first round of workshops will be followed by another round about a month apart to allow for analysis. In the second workshop, digital storytelling methods will be applied to capture scenarios in innovative formats. Four groups in each workshop will produce a digital story which describes each of the four scenarios. Each scenario workshop facilitator will be responsible for producing a report and a policy brief summarising the four scenario narratives developed for their theme, and indicating the solutions identified as desirable. FIBL will ensure user friendliness and production of summaries in English and associated native languages. Reports will include policy options for supporting desirable transition pathways.

At the end of the Scenario Development exercise, five Living Labs will be selected by the Rural Digitisation Forum to develop Use Cases on the solutions that have emerged during the scenario exercises. This activity will also comprise two workshops (*Use Case workshops*). Eventually, one Living Lab, selected for its high potential impact, will develop two Showcase technologies.

Table 11 integrates key information about the 20 Living Labs foreseen, although there may be some changes in this sense:

Table 9: Main Living Lab key stakeholders

#	Domain	Focal Question	MS	Region	Key stakeholders
1	AGRICULTURE: Functioning of markets and value chains	How to improve the logistics of local markets and enable the connection of two rural-urban areas?	NL	Flevoland	Local associations, municipalities, RABO-bank
2			LV	Latvia	Farmers organisations, consumers, farmers, local administrations, rural support service of Latvia
3			FR	Nouvelle Aquitaine, Bourgogne, Bretagne, Hauts de France, Centre	Agriculture and agri-food SMEs linked to France Clusters (franceclusters.fr)
4	AGRICULTURE and RURAL: Competitiveness and scalable opportunities for agricultural and rural businesses	How to improve the competitiveness of organic farming systems? How to introduce gender-sensitive technologies? How to improve the performance of SMEs located in rural areas?	EL	Central Greece	Farmers, advisors, researchers, American Farm School
5			CH	Rural areas in Switzerland	Farmers, advisors, researchers
6			HU	North Great Plain Region	Farmers, SMEs, advisors, researchers
7			UK-SCOT	Scotland	SMEs, local administrations, Scottish Crofting Federation
8			BE	West-Flanders	Actors of the intensive livestock production chain and policy makers
9	ES	Aragon	Actors of the intensive livestock production chain, policy makers		

10	RURAL: Quality of life in rural areas Employment	How to reduce the risk of floods in 2030?	IT	Tuscany	Local administrations, farmers, forest owners, Tuscany Regional Administration
11		How to improve the efficiency of water management in rural areas?	EL	Trikala region	Water utilities, regional administrations, city of Trikala
12		How to close the bioeconomy loop at regional level?	FI	Central Ostrobothnia	Farmers, biomass processors, public institutions, members of the Kokkola Industrial Park
13		How to facilitate co- design and co-decision on land use for energy production in rural areas? How to encourage women's involvement?	DE	Lake of Constance	Biogas producers, local institutions, farmers
14		How to connect sustainable small farmers to tourists and consumers?	HR	Croatian Adriatic Region	Public institutions, tourist board, hoteliers, private renters, local administrations, local farmers, farmer organisations, local action groups.
15		How to increase the communications possibilities across application domains in rural villages? How to facilitate access to women?	DE	Rhineland-Palatinate	Mayors, local communities, SMEs
16	RURAL: (re)deployment of public services	How to improve gerontology offer and services in rural areas?	FR	Nouvelle Aquitaine (Limoges) or Occitanie (Lot)	Local communities, stakeholders from the medical and health sector (gerontology), local authorities, research
17		How to enhance participation in rural planning? How to empower women?	PL	Specific municipalities in rural Poland	Municipalities, local communities, citizens

18	FORESTRY	How to reduce the risk of forest fires?	ES	Andalucia	Public administrations, local civil protection agency, fire fighters
19		How to provide digital tools to support the wood traceability over the whole process lifecycle/supply chain (in conformity to the compulsory EU Timber Regulation (995/2010)?	IT	Umbria	Forest owners, public administrations, forest industry and civil society
20			AT		Forest owners, public administrations, forest industry and civil society

6.4. Events

National level conferences, policy auditions and Living Lab workshops will develop skills and create awareness among key stakeholders on digitisation impacts.

These events will be tailored around maximising the 'Living Lab logic' (design thinking, co-creation sessions, visual and innovative reporting techniques) as well as the interconnection between offline and online audiences.

The Policy Briefs and the Policy Analysis and Roadmap report will have a considerable impact on policy makers at regional level, as they will be communicated through policy auditions, national conferences and the Rural Digitisation Forum. They are expected to affect policies at both EU and national levels.

In addition, DESIRA will develop a set of guidelines for workshops (both Scenario Development and Use Cases workshops), that will be included in the Training Kit. These will support local communities and stakeholder organisations willing to develop participatory events.

In order to ensure an effective communications and dissemination of the different actions, developments and results carried out within DESIRA project, the following communications elements (among others) could be implemented in all DESIRA workshops and events (Table 12):

Table 10. Communications elements associated to events

What?	When?	Where and how?	To whom?	Why?
Events (schedule & concept note)	Before event	DESIRA VRE	DESIRA Partners	Facilitate understanding among partners and ensure smooth organisation and preparation
Events (live tweeting)	During event	Social media	Broad public (on and offsite)	Create a link between event participants and other stakeholders

	Events surveys) (instant	During event	Specific tools (Sli.do)	Broad onsite	public	Create a link between speakers and event participants
	Events brochures) (event	During event	On-site distribution	Broad onsite	public	Disseminate the main findings of DESIRA in a visually appealing way
	Events (streaming)	During event	Website embedded or Facebook (YouTube repository when/if needed)	Offsite participants		Allow live dissemination to offsite participants
	Events (real-time visualisation)	During event	Social media, Live streaming	Event participants (on and offsite) and panel experts		Create a link between event participants and other stakeholders
	Events (online self-assessment)	During event	Online form	Event participants		Assess the event performance
	Media relations (Connect with networks)	Before event	E-mailing	Journalists		Improve connections with specialised and EU focused local press
	Media relations (Connect with newsrooms and agencies)	Before event	E-mailing	Journalists		Present the project, partners, key data/facts/figures, etc. Invite them to the event
	Media relations (press kit)	Before event	E-mailing	Journalists present at the event		Present the project, partners, key data/facts/figures, etc.
	Media relations (media list)	Before event	E-mailing	Journalists not present at the event		Present the project, partners, key data/facts/figures, etc.
	Editorial (short article/press release)	After event	DESIRA VRE, DESIRA website, webzine, social media	Citizen groups and local communities, policy makers		Ensure dissemination of main project messages, living lab focal questions, digital stories and use cases.
	Editorial (newsletter/webzine)	Before and after event	E-mailing	RDF members		Provide information on recent activities of DESIRA

	Branding (guidelines for facilitation)	Before the event	DESIRA VRE	DESIRA partners	Ensure smooth development of the events
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6.4.1. Policy Auditions

Policy Auditions are meetings organised by Living Labs, and specifically targeted at policy makers to discuss, refine and validate the results of the Scenario report synthesised into Policy Briefs. Together with the national conferences, they are an active means of disseminating these findings. The 20 Policy Auditions expect to attract the attendance of at least 400 participants.

6.4.2. National Conferences

A total of 15 national conferences will be organised. The target audience are policy makers at national level and relevant stakeholders (rural businesses, farmers and digital technology operators). The main objectives of the conferences are to disseminate the Policy Briefs and the Policy Analysis and Roadmap report and to create awareness among key actors on the digitisation impact by presenting the main findings of the project to a broader audience.

They are expected to attract at least **750 participants in total**. The details about each conference (location, venue, organisation, specific themes and objectives, target audience and participants) will be laid out in a Concept Note to facilitate understanding among partners. The monitoring and coordination of the conferences will be undertaken by an event organisation team within the DESIRA central unit under the supervision of UNIPI.

6.4.3. Regional workshops

A total of 60 regional workshops are expected to be implemented under the context of the work of the Living Labs with the aim of involving key actors in a learning process. They target mainly rural business and services, digital technology operators and farmers. Around 20 participants per workshop are expected.

6.4.4. Final DESIRA Conference

The final conference will provide a synthesis of the main policy and practice-oriented findings of the project, serving to increase the visibility of the project, foster the exploitation of results, and present it to the general public, target groups and relevant stakeholders.

This international event is therefore targeted mainly at policy makers, media and NGOs, with an expected attendance of at least 100 participants and the presence of 10 journalists, to whom dedicated press kits will be delivered.

The details about the final conference (location, venue, organisation, specific themes and objectives, target audience and participants) will be laid out in a Concept Note to facilitate understanding among partners. The monitoring and coordination of it will be undertaken by an event organisation team within the DESIRA central unit under the supervision of UNIPI.

6.5. Training

Webinars will be considered as training activities, as they will provide relevant insights to a more specific audience.

DESIRA will promote four Student Academies on Digitisation in rural areas. These comprise three editions of the [International Masters on Rural Development](#) (IMRD) and one ESRS winter course.

The IMRD is managed by three members of the consortium (UNIFI, UGENT, UCO) and will be dedicated, in 2019, 2020 and 2021 to the digitisation of the [IMRD Case Study in Tuscany](#). The Winter School on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) will be organised in 2022 in collaboration with European Society of Rural Sociology. Table 13 summarises the most relevant information about DESIRA training activities:

Table 11. Summary of training activities

Training activity	Partners involved WHO?	Description WHAT?	Date / Period WHEN?	Place WHERE?	Rationale WHY?	Results
Winter school	UNIFI, WU, BSC, ILVO, UCO, UJYV, KIT	ESRS Winter School on RRI	2022	Ghent (Belgium)	Contribute to professional development of researchers and other potential users of the knowledge generated by the project	20 students
International Master	UNIFI; UGENT, UCO	International Master on Rural Development	Four editions in 2019, 2020 and 2021	Tuscany (Italy)	Contribute to professional development of researchers and other potential users of the knowledge generated by the project	80 students
Webinars	AEIDL, all partners	Short online seminars on DESIRA outputs	Available from 2020	YouTube channel VRE	Gather relevant information about a number of topics and share it with both a specialised and a general audience	650 searches

7. Other communications elements

7.1. Branding

By using a unique visual identity throughout the consortium and all our communications products, we will ensure consistency in DESIRA communications and dissemination. Templates for different types of documents (e.g. MS Word, PPT, e-mail signature) will be prepared and made accessible to all those involved in DESIRA.

Templates are important to give a uniform image of the project and to establish a visual language that will indicate that the information presented derives from the DESIRA project. The DESIRA visual identity will comply with the visual guidelines of the European Commission.

The main elements of the visual identity package of DESIRA comprise:

- Logo
- Graphic Charter
- Template package (presentations, social media, documents, event communications and e-mail signature)

See Annex 1 for more information.

7.2. Campaigning

In order to maximise the project impact when relevant milestones occur (organisation of key events, production of policy briefs, etc.), DESIRA will carry out public relations campaigning actions so as to reach the crucial stakeholders at EU level, but also at national, regional and local levels.

This will be done by addressing key communications products (such as policy briefs, webinars or press releases) directly to the relevant target audiences identified, according to both to DESIRA calendar of milestones and eventually to particularly significant political momentums.

European **stakeholders** include, *inter alia*, MEPs from relevant Parliamentary Committees, CoR, EESC, regional and national rural development networks, European NGOs, Agricultural and Rural Development advocacy networks, etc.

In this sense, the project plans to carry out the following mapping actions:

- Mapping of MEPs: Parliamentary Committees to be primarily considered (and intergroups such as RUMRA)
 - DEVE: Development
 - ITRE: Industry, Research and Energy
 - REGI: Regional Development

- AGRI: Agriculture and Rural Development
- ENVI: Environment, Public Health and Food Safety
- TRAN: transport and tourism
- Mapping of other institutional stakeholders
 - Committee of the Regions
 - Units in other Directorates of the European Commission (DG AGRI, DG DIGIT, etc.)
 - ENRD contact point
 - EIP service point
 - European Economic and Social Committee
- Mapping of other stakeholders organisations
 - Broadband competence offices (BCO)
 - National Rural Networks
 - European networks involved in digitisation of rural areas (ELARD, EnoLL, Interreg projects, COpa-COGECA, CEJA, Euromontana, CEMR, etc.)
 - European Digital Service Infrastructures and Broadband Operators, including the WIFI4EU community, etc.

8. Exploitation of results

The partners have an obligation to exploit their results. “Each beneficiary must – up to four years after the period set out, as indicated in the Grant Agreement [GA] Article 3 – take measures aiming to ensure ‘exploitation’ of its results”.

In this regard, the Training Kit will form the basis for exploitation of the outputs. The methodologies developed during DESIRA (including those illustrated in the open access PEA, NEI, SESI and Comparative Scenario reports) will be made fully available to potential users through toolkits and training courses. DESIRA will also develop technological applications, which will be made available through Open Licences.

The exploitation strategy is conceived with a view to encouraging the exploitation of the results, for example by being incorporated into new innovation projects or into training courses. Table 14 provides an overview of the main project results forming DESIRA exploitation strategy, together with their target users and expected indicators.

Table 12. DESIRA exploitation Strategy

Project results	Measures to maximise impact	Target	Quantified indicators
D6.4 Training Kit	Adopting into toolkits and training courses	Students, community leaders	100 students trained with the training kit
D5.1 DESIRA Virtual Research Environment	Infrastructure service	Researchers, rural businesses and services, public authorities, citizen groups and local communities, digital technology operators, farmers, media	About 200 subscriptions during DESIRA, about 300 after the project
D5.2 DESIRA OpenAire Research Community Dashboard	Open Licence	Researchers, digital technology operators	About 500 searches and downloads
D5.4 Socio-Economic Assessment Tool	Open Licence	Researchers, digital technology operators, SMEs, farmers	More than 5 000 queries
D5.4 Digital Game Changers Taxonomy and Inventory Visualisation tool	Open Licence	Researchers, digital technology operators, SMEs, farmers	More than 5 000 queries
D3.4 Showcase Technologies (Virtual Farm Platform)	Proof of Concept	Researchers, digital technology operators, SMEs, farmers	More than 1 000 downloads

9. Communications team

The communications team is responsible for preparing the communications action plans, assessing the progress of it, planning the timing of the DECO outputs and checking the coherence of specific communications messages with the overarching DESIRA messages.

The communications team is composed as follows:

Coordination level 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">•Project Communications Manager, AEIDL•Project Communications Coordination, UNIPI•Project Communications Officer, Cultivate•IT Manager, CNR
Coordination level 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none">•Partners' Communications liaison officers (22) (one contact person per partner)

10. Quality Control

10.1. Guidelines

The project will entail an intense learning activity within the consortium and with its external circles. A series of guidelines for project deliverables will ensure the quality of the material produced within the project (Table 15).

Guidelines are initially addressed to project partners, and they intend to provide them with guidance, tools, recommendations and occasionally document templates for a smooth performance and quality result regarding the outputs of the project.

As per the RRI principle of ensuring gender equality, in both the research process and research content, the gender manager partner (Jame Hutton Institute - UK) will be consulted for developing guidelines that closely consider gender issues.

Table 13. DESIRA guidelines

Guidelines for...	Objective	Related actions	Lead partner	Support	Date/Period
Communications	To provide partners with a toolkit for the production of communication products (journal articles, social media, podcasts, etc.) and the preparation and organisation of events (national conferences, RDF meetings, etc.)	Brand templates (MS Word, PPT, etc.)	AEIDL	-	Month 12
Use Cases and Showcase Technology Practice Abstracts (6) in EIP format	Template - create homogeneity among project outcomes		ATHENA, CNR	AEIDL	Month 06
Policy Briefs (20) in EIP format	Template - create homogeneity among project outcomes		UCO, FIBL	INRA, AEIDL	Month 30
National policy reports	Template - create homogeneity among project outcomes		UCO	INRA	Month 24
Policy Auditions	To analyse the policy frameworks and the	Template for policy	UCO	INRA	Month 18-23

	initiatives, strategies and instruments affecting the digitisation of rural areas in each country	briefs and national policy reports			
Assessment of DGCs	To give guidance to partners to select and assess 300 projects (criteria)	Taxonomy of DGC	CNR	ILVO	Months 01-03
Socio-Economic Assessment	To provide an initial list of impact indicators and to give instructions on how to collect data, carry out workshops, measure indicators	Template for national reports	UNIPI	KIT ITAS, UGENT, UCO (policy issues) and HUTTON (gender issues)	Months 01-12
Living Labs Scenario Development and Use Case workshops	To carry out the scenario workshops and to draw the related reports for comparative analysis	Training for Living Lab leaders and workshop facilitators	HUTTON	UCO (policy issues) and HUTTON (gender issues)	Month 06-18
Training kit	To collect all training material developed throughout the project. Provide support for those willing to develop participatory events		AEIDL		Month 48

10.2. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

A combination of qualitative and quantitative indicators will be used to measure the results achieved by the DECO actions. All data will be compiled and evaluated regularly, and utilised to build indicators, which will be continuously checked throughout the project.

The key performance indicators are structured in a way that reflect the integrated nature of the DECO strategy. The KPIs outlined in the table below capture the performance of all the communication products developed by the project through the different communication channels. This enables us to monitor and better assess the contribution of the DECO activities towards achieving goals.

Most of the KPIs are built on the aggregation of the performance of individual communication actions, products and engagement activities. The KPIs are benchmarked against a set of goals and targets to enable the communications team determine the possible shortcomings and possible adjustments throughout the lifetime of the strategy. Quantification of target has been done considering the time of

publication of specific communication products³. Regular follow-up of the performance of the communications activities as regards the proposed KPIs will be carried out during the periodic communications meetings. When an issue is spotted, mitigation measures will be implemented. Nonetheless, a more detailed communication assessment will be carried out in M24 and M48 and which will include data on specific communication products. The table below presents the key KPI and the respective communication targets.

Table 14. KPIs

DECO Channels	Communication objectives	KPIs (at the end of the project) ⁴
Website	CO1 CO2 CO3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total number of unique visitors: – 22 000 by relevant web sections <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The project – 5 000 - Resources – 5 000 - Tools – 3 500 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ DGC ✓ Impact Assessment Tool ✓ VFP ✓ Others - News – 2 000 - Events – 1 500 - Living Labs – 2 000 - RDF – 3 000 • Total Number of documents downloaded by relevant web sections – 5 000 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The project – 2 000 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Project deliverables - Resources – 3 000 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Reports and working documents ✓ Scientific publications ✓ Research data ✓ Policy abstracts

³ Communication products will continue their function after the projects finalisation, so performance figures would be greater if considering a longer time period beyond M48.

⁴ Targets are different for the various communication products depending on the targeted audience and the timing in which they are finalised and disseminated.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Practice abstracts ✓ Training toolkit
Events	CO1 CO2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total number of participants in the events by type of event: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional workshops: 1 200 participants - National Conferences: 750 participants - Final conference: 100 participants - RDF meetings: 120 participants • Usefulness of events for participants (average) and by type of event: minimum 3 out of 4⁵
Webinar and videos	CO1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total participants in the webinars: 50 participants • Usefulness of the webinar to raise awareness and enhance capacities of the participants: minimum 3 out of 4⁶ • Number of views of the webinars: 750 views • Number of views of digital stories: 1 500 views
Rural Digitisation Forum	CO1 CO2 CO3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of Members of the RDF: 250 • Number of interactions in the RDF <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Working Groups: Number of exchanges in the VRE: 500 interactions - RDF on Facebook - Number of Posts from members: 200 posts - General RDF – Number of communications shared by DESIRA – 35 communications
Social Media	CO1 CO2 CO3	<p>Twitter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total number of impressions: 200 000 • Number of followers: 1 000 • Number of posts: 500 (including live tweets for events) <p>Facebook</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total number of impressions: 15 000

⁵ Being - 1 low usefulness and 4 highly useful

⁶ Being - 1 low usefulness and 4 highly useful

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total number of page likes: 300 Number of posts: 350 <p>LinkedIn</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total number of post impressions: 20 000 Total number of followers: 150 <p>YouTube</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of subscribers: 150 <p>Total number of views: 1500</p>
Newsletter	CO1 CO2 CO3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total number of subscribers: 600

10.3. Contingency Plan

The contingency plan is implemented and monitored by the communications team, in close relation to the lead coordinator. It feeds the project’s reporting duties and ensures that proper and immediate follow-up steps are taken to mitigate or solve the issue.

Table 15: Contingency plan

Risk for implementation	Level of Risk	Risk-mitigation measure
There is a gap between communications and research activities: researchers are too focused on research to get involved in communications, and tend to downplay obligations related to communications	Medium	Each partner has to nominate a contact person in charge of communications. A communications working group is set up to coordinate communications efforts
Research results are too complex to be communicated. Researchers tend to focus on their own objectives and on scientific language, and are not trained to identify effective messages to be communicated	Medium	The communications leader and co-leader will interact with researchers to identify the main messages. Templates for practice abstracts and policy briefs will be developed. Stories, videos, webinars and other products will be developed by communications experts
Setting up a Living Lab is more complex than expected	Medium	Commitment of key partners has been asked. Coordination and support for setting-up activities are planned

<p>Deliverables not contributing enough to the project objectives</p> <p>When focusing on their own tasks, researchers may tend to forget the overall objectives of the project. This may lead to good scientific results, but the fulfilment of the objectives can be undermined</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>DESIRA puts great emphasis on internal communications and continuous recall of general objectives. The conceptual framework has a coordination relevance as it creates space for collective learning and alignment between components of the project. The emphasis on communications to generate messages to the outside is another way of allowing researchers to focus on overall objectives</p>
<p>Project fails to meet the target KPI values for the different communicator (number of RDF members, social media engagement, number of scientific articles, website traffic, etc.)</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>The partners will establish SMART target values for the different KPIs developed to avoid this risk. In case of bad performance in a specific indicator, a tailored Action Plan will be devised by the communications team</p>
<p>Lack of consistency of communications products (layout, language, etc.)</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>Guidelines, quality control procedures and communications meetings will allow this risk to be overcome</p>

Annex 1. Visual identity

Elements of the corporate brand

The corporate brand «DESIRA» is presented in fixed proportion and defined typography. None of these characteristics should be varied. The logo typography is exclusive and in no case should you identify another element that is not the corporate brand itself.

Figure 2: Brand identifier

Security zone

The logo must always appear in proportionate dimensions. Always on WHITE colour, and in the event of coloured background or irregular areas, it must present the elements in full white or black, depending on the final contrast.

The Corporate Brand must appear with the least amount of graphic elements around it, since it could decrease its prominence and affect its readability. A minimum safety zone has been established, which marks the perimeter distance of the elements that make up the brand with its closest surroundings.

Figure 3: Security Zone

Minimum size

A minimum size for the brand has been determined. This ensures that the brand does not lose its personality or its readability.

Figure 4: Minimum size

Brand representation

If only black ink is used, it will appear in 100% Black. In case of reproducing the mark on a colour, illustrative or photographic background, it will be applied negatively on it. The brand may be used in white on its corporate colours if its environment requires it and for applications in which it has been proven that in this way its performance is optimal.

Figure 5: Brand representations

Basic colours

The corporate colours of the brand are PANTONE 356 and PANTONE 368.

It is recommended that the colours represented are direct, but otherwise, we specify a four-colour formula for proper use.

Figure 6: Basic colors

COLORES DIRECTOS

PORCENTAJES COLORES DIRECTOS

DIRECT COLORS

DIRECT COLOR PERCENTAGES

PANTONE 356

100%

10%

CUATRICROMÍA C: 87 M: 0 Y: 100 K: 34

RGB R: 0 G: 118 B: 40

HTML # 007628

PANTONE 356

100%

10%

CUATRICROMÍA C: 68 M: 0 Y: 100 K: 0

RGB R: 95 G: 173 B: 37

HTML # 5fad25

Other configurations

You can also make this type of brand configuration depending on the space and support where it is located.

Figure 7: Other configurations

Corporate typography

The typeface used in the «DESIRA» logo is the Syncopate family modified to a semibold, which is the main corporate typeface and is used for the name/logo.

Figure 8: Corporate typography

	FAMILIA SYNCOPATE
SYNCOPATE REGULAR	<p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz</p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz</p> <p>0123456789!>·\$%&/()=?¿[</p>
SYNCOPATE BOLD	<p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz</p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz</p> <p>0123456789!>·\$%&/()=?¿[</p>

Incorrect uses of the brand

Consistency in the use of the basic elements is essential to protect the impact and integrity of the visual identity. This section shows some examples of what CANNOT be done. The corporate brand «DESIRA» has been developed to establish quality and consistency in the presentation. It is the tool that allows you to project the image to an environment full of signs that can distort it. The specifications indicated here make it clear that the brand must not be manipulated in any of the cases.

Figure 9: Incorrect uses of the brand

NO INVADA LA ZONA DE SEGURIDAD
DO NOT INVITE THE SECURITY AREA

NO AÑADA OTROS ELEMENTOS A LA MARCA
DO NOT ADD OTHER ELEMENTS TO THE BRAND

NO VARÍE LAS PROPORCIONES DEL LOGOTIPO
DO NOT VARY THE PROPORTIONS OF THE LOGO

NO REINCORPORA LA MARCA DENTRO DE UNA FIGURA
DO NOT REINCORPORATE THE BRAND INSIDE OF A FIGURE

NO CAMBIE NINGUNO DE LOS COLORES
DO NOT CHANGE ANY OF THE COLORS

NO DISTORSIONE EL LOGOTIPO, NO CAMBIE LAS TIPOGRAFÍAS
DO NOT DISTORGE THE LOGO, DO NOT CHANGE THE TYPOGRAPHS

Annex 2. Abbreviations

AKIS: Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
CA: Consortium Agreement
CAF: Conceptual Analytical Framework
COs: Communications Objectives
CSA: Comparative Scenario Assessment
DESIRA: Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts In Rural Areas
DECO: Dissemination, Exploitation, Communications and Outreach
EIP: European Innovation Partnership
EP: Exploitation Plan
GA: Grant Agreement
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation
ICTs: Information and Communications Technology
IPR: Intellectual Property Rights
LLs: Living Labs
NEI: Needs, Expectations and Impacts
PAs: Practice Abstracts
PEA: Pan-European Report on Rural Digitisation
POs: Project Objectives
RDF: Rural Digitisation Forum
RRI: Responsible Research and Innovation
SCPS: Socio-Cyber-Physical Systems
SDG: Sustainable Development Goals
SESI: Socio-Economic Sustainability Indicators
SM: Social Media
TGC: Taxonomy of Game changers
VFP: Virtual Farm Platform
VRE: Virtual Research Environment

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